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Application of RUSLE Integrated with GIS and Remote Sensing Techniques to Assess Soil Erosion in Uyo and Its Environs in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20303101>

Citation: Ikediuwa, S. C., Okenwa, A. I., Ugwu, C. M., Uzodimma, C. C., & Adejoh, F. (2026). Application of RUSLE Integrated with GIS and Remote Sensing Techniques to Assess Soil Erosion in Uyo and Its Environs in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Modern Research and Emerging Trends*, 2(3). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20303101>

Abstract

Soil erosion is a major environmental challenge that threatens sustainable land management, particularly in tropical regions where intense rainfall and human activities accelerate land degradation. This study assesses soil loss in Uyo and its environs, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, using an integrated Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Remote Sensing (RS) approach based on the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE). The study utilised both primary and secondary datasets, including 39 years (1986–2024) of monthly rainfall data from NASA, Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI) imagery, and a 30 m resolution ASTER Global Digital Elevation Model (GDEM). In addition, 50 soil samples were collected and analysed to estimate soil erodibility. The RUSLE model was implemented in ArcGIS 10.5 by integrating rainfall erosivity (R), soil erodibility (K), slope length and steepness (LS), cover-management (C), and conservation practice (P) factors. Results revealed that rainfall erosivity ranged from 667.75 to 943.86 MJ mm ha⁻¹ h⁻¹ yr⁻¹, with higher values in the southern part of the study area. Soil erodibility values varied between 0.039 and 0.078, while the LS factor showed higher values in areas of steep terrain. NDVI-based analysis indicated that sparsely vegetated areas are more

prone to erosion. The P factor was assumed to be 1, reflecting minimal conservation practices. Estimated annual soil loss ranged from 0 to 2694.39 tons/ha/yr, with a mean of 5.68 tons/ha/yr. High erosion risk zones were widespread, especially in areas with steep slopes and disturbed surfaces. These findings highlight the need for effective soil conservation and improved land-use planning in the study area.

Keywords: soil loss, GIS, remote sensing, RUSLE model

1.0 Introduction

Soil erosion remains one of the most critical environmental challenges affecting sustainable land management worldwide. It is a major form of land degradation that reduces soil fertility, decreases agricultural productivity, and contributes to sedimentation in rivers and reservoirs (FAO & ITPS, 2015). Globally, accelerated soil loss driven by anthropogenic activities such as deforestation, urban expansion, and intensive agriculture has significantly exceeded natural soil formation rates, particularly in developing countries (Pimentel & Burgess, 2013). In tropical regions, high rainfall intensity combined with fragile soils and improper land-use practices further exacerbates erosion processes.

In Nigeria, soil erosion constitutes a serious environmental and socio-economic problem, especially in the southern states where high precipitation and unconsolidated coastal plain sands increase susceptibility to runoff and gully formation (Igwe, 2005). The south-eastern and south-southern regions have experienced severe land degradation due to rapid urbanisation, poor drainage systems, and vegetation loss. Akwa Ibom State, characterised by a humid tropical climate and intense seasonal rainfall, is particularly susceptible to soil erosion hazards. Increasing population pressure and infrastructure development around Uyo have intensified land surface disturbances, making systematic soil loss assessment essential for effective planning and environmental protection.

Traditional methods of measuring soil erosion are often time-consuming, expensive, and spatially limited. However, the integration of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Remote Sensing (RS) techniques has significantly improved the accuracy and efficiency of soil erosion modelling. GIS provides a powerful platform for spatial data integration, analysis, and visualisation, while remote sensing offers reliable temporal and spatial datasets for monitoring land use/land cover dynamics (Wischmeier & Smith, 1978; Renard et al., 1997). Satellite imagery enables the derivation of critical

erosion parameters such as vegetation cover, slope gradient, rainfall intensity, and soil characteristics.

Among the various empirical models developed for estimating soil loss, the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) has been widely adopted due to its relative simplicity, adaptability, and compatibility with GIS environments (Renard et al., 1997). The RUSLE model estimates average annual soil loss by integrating rainfall erosivity (R), soil erodibility (K), slope length and steepness (LS), cover-management (C), and conservation practice (P) factors. When combined with spatial datasets derived from remote sensing and digital elevation models (DEMs), RUSLE provides a practical approach for erosion risk assessment at watershed and regional scales (Ganasri & Ramesh, 2016).

Despite the increasing application of GIS-based soil, erosion modelling globally, only a few studies have comprehensively quantified soil loss in Uyo and its environs using integrated geospatial techniques. Given the rapid urban growth and environmental changes occurring in the area, there is a need for spatially explicit erosion risk assessment to guide land-use planning, soil conservation strategies, and sustainable environmental management.

Therefore, this study aims to estimate soil loss using GIS and remote sensing techniques in Uyo and its environs, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to derive RUSLE model parameters using geospatial datasets, map the spatial distribution of soil erosion risk, and identify areas requiring urgent conservation intervention. The findings will contribute to improved environmental decision-making and sustainable land resource management in the study area.

2.0 Study Area

Uyo and its environs are the study area. Akwa Ibom State is situated in the southern coastal region of Nigeria, with an estimated population of approximately five million people. Notably, it is recognised as the leading oil and gas-producing state in the country. The state shares its southern boundary with the Atlantic Ocean, along a coastline that stretches for about 129 kilometres, extending from Ikot Abasi in the west to Oron in the east. This expansive ocean frontage positions Akwa Ibom as a significant coastal zone in Nigeria, characterised by mangrove forests and sandy beaches. The study area encompasses eight local government areas within Akwa Ibom State surrounding Uyo.

Uyo Local Government Area (LGA) is the capital city of Akwa Ibom State. Uyo was the district headquarters during the colonial era and later upgraded to a Local Government area and the state capital in 1987. The United Nations Population Projection, which runs to 2035, projects that the current metro area population of Uyo in 2024 is 1,393,000, a 4.82% increase from 2023. The study area lies between latitudes $4^{\circ} 40'$ and $5^{\circ} 20'$ North of the Equator and longitudes $7^{\circ} 40'$ and $8^{\circ} 10'$ East of the Greenwich Meridian.

Figure 2.1. Map of study area

3.0 Data source

Primary data

Primary data sources include meteorological records of rainfall variation (monthly), which are compiled to provide annual rainfall data for the study area from the National

Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) repository. The soil samples were obtained from the field, and their GPS location is a sample of ground truth location for erodibility computation.

Rainfall Data

The rainfall data used were retrieved weather data with corresponding meteorological, temporal, and spatial features from the NASA repository (Power, 2022). The rainfall data used for this work were from 1986 to 2024, the monthly average data.

Secondary data

Multispectral Satellite Imagery

Optical multispectral imagery from Landsat was used for this study. The LANDSAT data were downloaded from USGS Earth Explorer, the United States Geological Survey (USGS) and the NASA Earth Observatory website. The Landsat satellite images used for this work were the Operational Land Imager (OLI) for 2024. The Landsat image scenes that covered the entire study area were path 188, rows 56 and 57. The image was of a 30m resolution. The data was used for the NDVI and C factor computation of the study area.

Digital Elevation Model

Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER) Global Digital Elevation Model (GDEM) version 2, a product of METI and NASA, was used for this study with a 30m resolution. ASTER GDEM was generated using stereo-pair images collected by the ASTER instrument onboard Terra. ASTER GDEM coverage spans from 83 degrees north latitude to 83 degrees south, encompassing 99 percent of Earth's landmass.

4.0 Method

Soil loss plays a fundamental role in the initiation and expansion of gully erosion. When the protective topsoil layer is removed, often due to intense surface runoff, poor land management, or lack of vegetation, exposed subsoils become highly susceptible to concentrated water flow. This process sets the stage for gully development, especially in areas with steep slopes or easily erodible soil types. Excessive soil loss is not only a consequence but also a precondition that accelerates and sustains gully formation and expansion over time (Martins *et al.*, 2022).

The average annual soil loss of the study area has been determined using the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) in an ArcGIS environment. RUSLE is an empirical model that has been applied worldwide to estimate soil erosion loss by using five

input parameters. These five factors would be multiplied by applying the following empirical equation in ArcGIS 10.5 using the raster calculator. Mathematically, equation (1) is denoted as:

$$A=R*K*LS*C*P \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where;

- A = annual soil loss (metric tons ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹),
- R = rainfall erosivity factor (MJ mm h⁻¹ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹),
- K = soil erodibility factor (metric tons ha⁻¹ MJ⁻¹ mm⁻¹),
- LS = slope length and steepness factor (dimensionless)
- C = land cover and management factor (dimensionless) and
- P = conservation practice factor (dimensionless).

The soil loss was implemented using the method shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Flowchart methodology

Rainfall Erosivity Factor (R)

The ability of erosion agents to cause soil detachment and transport is called erosivity. This erosivity factor R was calculated based on 39 years of rainfall data recorded at six stations, which exist around the study area, using the equation developed by Wischmeier and Smith (1978).

$$R = \sum_{i=1}^{12} 1.735 \times 10^{(1.5 \log \frac{P_i^2}{P} - 0.8188)}$$

Where R is a rainfall erosivity factor (MJ mm ha⁻¹ h⁻¹ per year); P_i is the monthly rainfall (mm); P is an annual rainfall (mm). The mean annual rainfall (P) of the study area was first interpolated to generate continuous rainfall data for each grid cell, estimated using the 'Inverse Distance Weight' method of interpolation in ArcGIS 10.5. To compute the rainfall erosivity factor, the inputs used are point datasets, such as the locational coordinate of the rain gauge station and the rainfall erosivity value calculated using the equation above. ArcMap cannot read data in degrees-minutes-seconds (DMS), and therefore, these data were converted into decimal degrees (DD) before importing using the Add XY tool in ArcGIS 10.5 to generate the point map of the rainfall erosivity before interpolation using the IDW method to generate the continuous erosivity data raster cell.

The IDW spatial analyst tool in ArcGIS 10.5 takes the concept of spatial autocorrelation literally. It assumes that the nearer a sample point is to the cell whose value is to be estimated, the more closely the cell's value will resemble the sample point's value. In the process of interpolation, 39 years of rainfall data for 6 rain gauge stations were used.

Erodibility Factor (K)

The soil erodibility is a measure of the susceptibility of soil particles to detachment and transport by rainfall and runoff. The erodibility factor was computed from the soil sample analysis and calculation (Songu *et al.*, 2021). The soil sample collection approach employed in this work, was to ensure representative coverage of each geological unit, based on the premise that soil erosion rates vary depending on soil type and influencing factors. Additionally, the sampling aimed to achieve a broad spatial distribution across the study area. A systematic sampling strategy was designed in alignment with the Local Government Areas encompassed within the study boundaries. Sampling points were selected from various villages to ensure a well-distributed representation throughout the area.

A total of 50 soil samples were collected across the study area, comprising 25 main samples and 25 corresponding composite samples. This approach was adopted to enhance the accuracy of soil erodibility estimation across the region. At each sampling location, two soil samples were collected at different depths, 0–15 cm and 0–45 cm, using a soil auger. A GPS receiver was employed to record the exact coordinates of each sampling point. Additionally, village names, specific site identifiers, and the date of collection were documented to facilitate the creation of a comprehensive soil database for the study. The samples were immediately taken to the laboratory for air drying each day of field operation to maximise changes in the concentration of extractable nutrients and some organic constituents.

The erodibility factor was computed using the formula:

$$K = \frac{2.8 \times 10^{-5} \times M^{1.14} \times (12 - a) + 0.43 \times (b - 2) + 3.3 \times (c - 3)}{100}$$

$$M = (\% \text{ silt} + \% \text{ very fine sand}) \times (100 - \% \text{ clay})$$

where M is particle-size parameter, a is % of soil organic matter content, b is soil structure code (1 = very fine granular; 2 = fine granular; 3 = medium or coarse granular; 4 = blocky, platy, or massive), and c is profile permeability (saturated hydraulic conductivity) class [1 = rapid (150 mmh^{-1}); 2 = moderate to rapid ($50\text{--}150 \text{ mmh}^{-1}$); 3 = moderate ($12\text{--}50 \text{ mmh}^{-1}$); 4 = slow to moderate ($5\text{--}15 \text{ mmh}^{-1}$); 5 = slow ($1\text{--}5 \text{ mmh}^{-1}$); 6 = very slow ($<1 \text{ mmh}^{-1}$)].

The erodibility factor (K): soil samples of the study area were interpolated to generate a continuous erodibility factor for each grid cell, estimated using the ‘Inverse Distance Weight’ method of interpolation in ArcGIS 10.5.

The effect of topography on soil erosion has been estimated by the slope length (L) and slope steepness (S). To get the topographic factor of the study area, it was implemented in four steps. (i) Generation of flow direction, (ii) flow accumulation, (iii) slope degree, and (iv) topographic factor generation using the formula.

The flow direction determines the direction of flow from every cell in the raster DEM. This was done with the Flow Direction tool in ArcGIS 10.5. This tool takes the fill DEM as input and outputs a raster showing the direction of flow out of each cell. If the output drop raster option is chosen, an output raster is created showing a ratio of the maximum change in elevation from each cell along the direction of flow to the path length

between centres of cells and is expressed in percentages. There are eight valid output directions relating to the eight adjacent cells into which flow could travel (Jenson & Domingue, 1988). To generate the flow accumulation, the flow direction was used as an input using the flow accumulation tool in the software. The flow accumulation creates a raster of accumulated flow into each cell. The slope degree raster was generated from the fill DEM as input using the slope tool in ArcGIS 10.5. To generate the topographic factor, the equation below was implemented using the raster calculator in ArcGIS 10.5.

$$LS = \text{Power}(\text{Flow accumulation} * \text{cellsize} / 22.1, 0.6) * \text{Power}(\text{Sin}(\text{Slope} * 0.01745) / 0.09, 1.3)$$

Cover Management Factor (C)

The cover management factor reflects the proportion of soil loss occurring under a specific type of vegetation compared to that on bare soil. It serves as an indicator of the extent to which a particular land cover protects the soil from erosion. The value of C depends on vegetation type, stage of growth, and cover percentage. The C factor was derived using the NDVI. The linear equation developed by Sulisty (2016) was implemented with the raster calculator in ArcGIS 10.5.

$$C = 0.6 - 0.77 \text{ NDVI} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

The C factor values vary between 0 and 1 based on the types of land cover.

Support Practice Factor

The support practice factor reflects the extent to which different agricultural practices influence the rate of soil loss. It evaluates the effectiveness of specific soil conservation methods, such as contour farming, strip cropping, and terracing, in reducing surface runoff and controlling soil loss (Amsalu and Mengaw, 2014). These practices play a critical role in mitigating erosion within cultivated landscapes. The P-value ranges from 0 to 1 depending on the soil management activities employed in the specific plot of land. These management activities are highly dependent on the slope of the area. The P-factor is calculated for agricultural land only, and for all other land use, it is assumed as 1. Because there are no control practice measures within the agricultural land in the study area, the P-factor value was assumed as 1.

Annual Soil Loss

The final soil loss magnitude was obtained by analysing five geo-environmental factors: the Rainfall-Runoff Erosivity factor (R), the Soil-Erodibility factor (K), the Slope length (L) and Slope Steepness (S), the Cover management factor (C), and the Support Practice factor (P). The annual soil loss of the study area was computed using the five-factor map: R, K, LS, C and P as input in ArcGIS 10.5. The raster maps were integrated using the raster calculator tool in ArcGIS 10.5 to generate the soil loss map of the estimated study area.

5.0 Results and Discussion

This study utilises the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) model, integrated within a Geographic Information System (GIS) and Remote Sensing (RS) framework. This approach enables a cell-by-cell quantification of the mean annual soil loss rate and maps erosion-prone areas across the study site. The derivation and analysis of the raster-based RUSLE parameters are detailed in the following sections below.

Rainfall Erosivity Factor (R)

The rainfall map and rainfall erosivity map of the study area are presented in Figures 2 and 3, respectively. It was observed that the highest rainfall occurred in the south-western part of the study area, Uyo and Etinan LGA of the study area, with erosivity value peaking at $943.86 \text{ MJ mm h}^{-1} \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and declining toward the northern hinterland, reaching a minimum in Ibiono Ibom with an erosivity value of $667.75 \text{ MJ mm h}^{-1} \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. This trend is consistent with coastal influence, which typically drives the heavy and erosive rainfall patterns observed in Figure 3 in the southern portion of the state.

Figure 2: Rainfall map of the study area. Figure 3: Rainfall erosivity map of the study area

Soil Erodibility Factor (K)

Soil erodibility refers to the degree to which soil is susceptible to erosion. The erodibility factor (K) was estimated based on soil texture, soil structure, organic matter content, and soil permeability. Several intrinsic soil properties were determined through laboratory analyses, including particle size analysis and aggregate size distribution. The calculated soil erodibility values ranged from 0.039, indicating low erodibility, to 0.078, representing high erodibility. Figure 4 shows the erodibility factor of the study area.

Figure 4: Soil erodibility of the study area

Topographic Factor (LS)

Topographic factors represent the effect of slope length and slope steepness on erosion under given conditions. Most of the study areas had low LS factor values, whereas very few locations had high LS factor values. The LS factor values range from 0 to 1094.68. The high values may be due to highly dissected terrain with abrupt slope changes in a few locations of the study area. The higher LS factor values were scattered and observed in hilly and gully areas with steep topography, and these areas are more prone to erosion and soil loss. The fact remains that Akwa Ibom State is relatively flat with undulating terrain in a few regions of the state, including Itu, Ibiono Ibom and part of Uyo LGA. Areas with a high degree of steepness were observed to experience soil loss even with slight and moderate amounts of rainfall and soil disturbance. High values of slope steepness were

observed in Itu, Ibiono Ibom and Uyo Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State.

Figure 5: Topographic factor of the study area

Cover Management Factor (C)

The cover management (C) factor values were derived from the normalised difference vegetation index as shown in Figure 6 below. The NDVI shows the level of presence of vegetative cover around the study area. A high C factor indicates no cover effect and, as such, a high erosion probability due to the high vulnerability of the soil surface to erosive forces, as shown in Figure 7 below. Lower C factor values indicate a good vegetation cover effect with negligible erosion, hence little or no soil loss. In the study area, bare surfaces

with very low NDVI values were seen to be highly prone to erosion, whereas the forested areas with high NDVI values were less prone to soil loss.

Figure 6: NDVI map of the study area

Figure 7: Cover management factor of the study area

Conservation Practice Factor (P)

The conservation practice factor represents the index of erosion control based on erosion control practices. The conservation practice factor value ranges from 0 to 1, with a value of 1 indicating no conservation practice in place. During the site inspection and ground truthing exercise, it was observed that there was really no practical effort to control soil erosion in almost all parts of the study area. A large portion of the study area was built up, farmland and forested land, and had no support or erosion control practices, giving it a support practice factor of 1.0.

Annual Soil Loss (A)

The annual soil loss from the RUSLE model. The RUSLE sub-factors (R, K, LS, C and P factors) were integrated into the equation by multiplying them together in a GIS environment to obtain the average annual soil loss A within the study area. Estimated soil loss rates ranged from 0 (zero) to 2694.39 tonnes/ha/yr, and the average soil loss rate was estimated at 5.68 tonnes/ha/yr. The results obtained from the analysis indicated that high and extreme sections of erosion vulnerability were scattered all over the entire study area, and every part of the study area had some level of erosion severity. The higher values of soil erosion were found to occur on abrupt slopes. Those regions with higher slopes were also affected by rills, gullies and ravines, as well as mass movement of sediments, which were clearly visible during field surveys. Rill erosion, gully erosion and mass transportation of sediments around those regions are a common phenomenon due to the fragile geomorphology of the region and land use practices.

6.0 Conclusion

Environmental and anthropogenic factors have contributed maximally to soil erosion within the study area. Rainfall, topography, soil type, and land use/land cover were the major factors responsible for severe soil loss in the area. Topography adversely affected soil loss in the north and northeast of the study area. Areas with steep slopes and rugged topography were prone to heavy soil loss. The result of rainfall analysis in the study area showed that rainfall was high in Uyo and Etinan LGAs with high erosivity values. The study area has a rainfall pattern that increases southward. The result of this research will play a vital role in policy and decision-making and will help planners in taking measures toward the management of soil erosion hazards.

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